

MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE LEARNING ORIENTATION ON THE EFFECT OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEE SUSTAINABLE PERFORMANCE

DÖNÜŞÜMCÜ LİDERLİĞİN ÇALIŞANIN SÜRDÜRÜLEBİLİR PERFORMANSINA ETKİSİNDE ÇALIŞANIN ÖĞRENME ORYANTASYONUNUN ARACI ROLÜ

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Abstract

Businesses worldwide are increasingly prioritizing sustainability to endure and prosper, engaging in fierce competition in this area. In today's competitive and dynamic environment, the enduring success of enterprises relies on the adoption and execution of an effective leadership strategy to improve employee performance. Transformational leadership has received much focus in management studies, especially about its influence on employee performance. Transformational leadership is essential for attaining corporate objectives by enhancing employee engagement and learning capacity, thereby elevating both individual and organizational performance. This study examines the impact of transformational leadership on employees' sustainable performance and explores the mediating function of learning orientation in this relationship. The research utilized data gathered from 302 employees of a textile firm in Elazığ Province. The analyses were conducted using the SPSS program, and the mediation effect was tested using the Process Macro analysis method developed by Hayes (2018). Model 4, which is suitable for the research model within the framework of variable models, was also tested. Model 4 consists of X (independent variable), M (mediator variable), Y (dependent variable). The findings indicate that transformational leadership favorably affects employees' sustainable performance, with learning orientation serving as a mediating factor in this relationship. The findings underscore the significance of implementing transformational leadership principles and facilitating employees' learning processes to maintain performance levels.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, sustainable performance, learning orientation, employee performance, human resources

Özet

Küresel ölçekte işletmeler hayatta kalmak ve gelişmek için sürdürülebilirliğe giderek daha fazla öncelik veriyor ve bu alanda yoğun bir rekabet içindeler. Bu rekabetçi ve hızla değişen dünyada işletmelerin sürdürülebilir başarıları çalışan performanslarını arttırmaya yönelik etkili bir liderlik yaklaşımını benimsemelerine ve uygulamalarına bağlıdır. Bu yaklaşımlar arasından dönüşümsel liderlik, özellikle çalışan performansındaki etkisi yönüyle yönetim araştırmalarında kapsamlı ilgi görmektedir. Dönüşümsel liderlik, çalışanların motivasyonunu ve öğrenme potansiyelini artırarak, gerek bireysel gerekse organizasyonel performansta artış sağlayarak, organizasyonel hedeflere ulaşmada kritik bir rol oynamaktadır. Bu bağlamda, bu araştırma, dönüşümsel liderliğin çalışanların sürdürülebilir performansları üzerindeki etkisini ve bu ilişkide öğrenme yöneliminin aracılık rolünü incelemektedir. Çalışma, Elazığ ilindeki bir tekstil firmasında çalışan 302 katılımcıdan elde edilen verilerle gerçekleştirilmiştir. Analizler SPSS programı kullanılarak yapılmış, aracılık etkisi Hayes (2018) tarafından geliştirilen Process Makro analiz yöntemi ile test edilmiştir. Değişken modelleri çerçevesinde araştırma modeline uygun olan model 4 de test edilmiştir. Model 4; X(bağımsız değişken), M(aracı değişken), Y(bağımlı değişken) şeklinde oluşmaktadır. Elde edilen sonuçlara göre, dönüşümsel liderlik çalışanların sürdürülebilir performansını pozitif yönde etkilemekte, aynı zamanda öğrenme yönelimi bu ilişkide aracılık rolü üstlenmektedir. Bulgular, dönüşümsel liderlik ilkelerinin

benimsenmesinin ve çalışanların öğrenme süreçlerine destek verilmesinin çalışan performansını sürdürülebilir kılmada önemli olduğunu göstermektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Dönüşümsel liderlik, sürdürülebilir performansı, öğrenme yönelimi, çalışan performansı, insan kaynakları

Introduction

In the contemporary global landscape, success is a fundamental pillar for businesses across many industries, strongly dependent on their capacity to change structurally, execute proactive management techniques, acquire resources, and develop intangible capabilities. (Martínez-Martínez, Madueno, Jorge & Sancho, 2017; Masa'deh, Al-Henzab, Tarhini & Obeidat, 2018). In competitive and rapidly changing contexts, firms must prioritize their human resources, seeing them as strategic assets essential for attaining objectives. Organizations with experienced, knowledgeable, and competent personnel are more adept at flourishing in an era of perpetual change, as human resources are essential for operational effectiveness and efficiency. (Mosadeghrad, 2003).

Leadership is continually highlighted as an essential component in the process of accomplishing corporate goals and preserving competitiveness, according to ongoing research. In addition to facilitating the development and execution of plans that guarantee sustained success, leadership ensures that people and material resources are aligned simultaneously (Fiaz, Su, Ikram & Saqib, 2017; Jing & Avery, 2016). By exerting their influence and providing strategic direction, leaders motivate their people to achieve exceptional achievements, which in turn improves the overall performance of the organization (Para-González, Jimenez & Martinez-Lorente, 2018). Effective leadership enhances goal attainment by cultivating robust, effective relationships between leaders and employees (Kim & Beehr, 2018).

Many firms have made the transition from transactional to transformational leadership styles in order to fulfill their strategic goals. This is done in order to meet the demands of a dynamic global market (Bass, 1999; Judge & Piccolo, 2004; Barling, Slater & Kelloway, 2010). Empirical data demonstrates the beneficial effect of transformational leadership on employee job performance, underscoring its importance in fostering a motivated, loyal, and high-performing workforce (Al-Amin, 2017; Mangkunegara & Huddin, 2016). Furthermore, transformational leadership fosters a collaborative and empowered work environment by adeptly reconciling company aims with employee welfare (Jung, Chan, Chen & Chow, 2010). Transformational leaders are characterized by vitality, proactivity, and knowledge, inspiring teams to adopt change and confront competitive problems with increased effort (Ahangar, 2009). This leadership style drives positive transformation by motivating employees to achieve

their utmost potential and enhance organizational development (López-Cabarcos, Vázquez-Rodríguez & Quiñoá-Piñero, 2022). Transformational leaders establish pathways for achieving long-term organizational objectives by providing strategic guidance, encouraging collaboration, and establishing a shared vision (McShane & Glinow, 2003). Additionally, transformational leadership effectively confronts both internal and external obstacles by emphasizing the organization's long-term development and adaptability, as well as that of its employees.

Enhancing performance is fundamental to competitiveness in the contemporary business landscape, reflecting an organization's ability to adapt and thrive (Wagner & Hollenbeck, 2020). Research confirms the substantial impact of leadership styles on individual and organizational results, encompassing job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behaviors, and overall productivity (Aboramadan & Dahleez, 2020; Lai, Tang, Lu, Lee & Lin, 2020; Tian, Iqbal, Akhtar, Qalati, Anwar & Khan, 2020). The correlation between employee performance and organizational success necessitates the selection of an effective leadership style for sustained competitiveness (Manzoor, Wei, Nurunnabi, Subhan, Shah & Fallatah, 2019).

Transformational leadership, defined by its emphasis on motivating, enabling, and transforming employees, creates robust connections with job happiness and performance. Job performance, as a quantifiable behavior essential for goal attainment, enhances resource efficiency and fosters sustainable organizational outcomes (Ng, 2017). This leadership style profoundly impacts employee attitudes and behaviors, rendering it essential in modern corporate operations (Gao, Murphy & Anderson, 2020). Transformational leadership, informed by social cognitive theory, emphasizes self-regulation and intrinsic motivation, promoting personal development and a feeling of purpose in employees (Wang, Huei & Ming, 2014). In this situation, a dedication to learning and skill enhancement is essential. Learning orientation, characterized by a commitment to improving one's talents, is crucial for strengthening employee performance (Dweck, 2000). Organizations can attain sustainable performance by seeing human resources as strategic assets. The favorable association between advanced education and enhanced employee results highlights the importance of ongoing growth in achieving corporate success.

Therefore, this study investigates the impact of transformational leadership on employees' sustainable performance, focusing on the mediating role of learning orientation.

Literature Review

Transformational Leadership (TL)

Transformational leadership has attained significant importance in management literature owing to its motivational and relational attributes (Gardner & Avolio, 1998). The fundamental concepts of transformational leadership theory were initially presented by Burns (1978) and subsequently elaborated by Bass (1985), who significantly advanced its development.

Burns (1978) characterized transformational leadership as the ability of leaders to motivate their followers to place organizational objectives above individual interests (Kuhnert & Lewis, 1987). Transformational leaders employ a supporting and guiding methodology, treating their followers equitably, providing assistance when necessary, disseminating knowledge, increasing abilities, and cultivating a feeling of justice (Bass, 1985; Hall, Johnson, Wysocki & Kepner, 2008). Transformational leaders, as noted by Bass (1994), Bass & Avolio (1994), and Hartog, Muijen & Koopman (1997), endeavor to realize the complete potential of their followers, fulfill their elevated needs, and foster robust value systems, ethical standards, and drive. These initiatives motivate followers to synchronize their ambitions with organizational aims, reevaluate their values and beliefs, and transcend personal interests to attain collective success (Bass, 1999, 1994; Bycio, Hackett & Allen, 1995; Rafferty & Griffin, 2004).

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The conceptual framework of transformational leadership is organized around four fundamental dimensions. (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Bass, 1999):

- *Inspirational Motivation*: According to the definition provided by Hartog et al. (2003), inspiration is characterized by the ability of the leader to act as an example for those who report to them. This aspect places an emphasis on the manner in which leaders motivate their teams to accomplish both individual and organizational objectives. According to Yammarino and Dubinsky (1994), effective leaders are able to express a vision that is both clear and compelling, while also demonstrating confidence, optimism, excitement, and motivational examples that invigorate their leaders' followers (p.791).
- *Idealized Influence*: This dimension highlights the fact that, according to the definition provided by Hartog et al. (2003), inspiration is characterized by the ability of the leader

to act as an example for those who report to them. This aspect places an emphasis on the manner in which leaders motivate their teams to accomplish both individual and organizational objectives. According to Yammarino and Dubinsky (1994), effective leaders are able to express a vision that is both clear and compelling, while also demonstrating confidence, optimism, excitement, and motivational examples that invigorate their leaders' followers. Charismatic behaviors of leaders, which are grounded in their values, beliefs, and sense of mission (Antonakis, Avolio & Sivasubramaniam, 2003). Leaders exhibiting idealized influence emphasize collective goals, ethical decision-making, and the importance of shared values and purpose (Avolio, 2005).

- *Individualized Consideration*: According to Dionne, Yammarino, Atwater, and Spangler (2004), leaders who practice personalized consideration have the tendency to approach each follower as a distinct individual rather than as a member of a general group. In order to fulfill the special requirements of their followers, they provide them with direction, assistance, and individualised inspiration, which ultimately leads to the encouragement of their growth.
- *Intellectual Stimulation*: Intellectual stimulation denotes a leader's capacity to provoke followers' ideas, values, and methodologies for problem-solving. According to Hartog et al. (1997), this component motivates followers to critically assess their own assumptions and beliefs, along with those of their leaders, so promoting creativity and innovation.

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Transformational leadership is acknowledged as an effective management approach for attaining organizational success (Krishnan, 2004). Transformational leadership cultivates a sense of unity and identity among employees by transforming their attitudes, beliefs, and ambitions, while also delivering a clearer articulation of the organization's vision, mission, and objectives. This leadership strategy yields favorable modifications in employment attitudes and behaviors, including increased corporate citizenship behavior, heightened commitment, higher performance, and sustained employee productivity (Yücel, 2021). Moreover, transformational leadership improves employee satisfaction with supervisors and positively affects perceived group performance, rendering its effective implementation essential for both individual and organizational results (Garcia, Moya, Molero & Moriano, 2016). Transformational leaders motivate their subordinates by their behaviors and words, promoting creativity, inventiveness, and a sense of belonging, which collectively improve job performance (Ferozi & Chang, 2021).

Employee Sustainable Performance (ESP)

In recent decades, the significance of sustainable organizations has markedly increased. Sustainability aims to attain equilibrium among economic development, environmental preservation, and social well-being. Numerous research have yielded definitions and insights into the nascent idea of employee sustainable performance, as articulated by authors such as Ji, Jonge, Peeters, and Taris (2021).

Employee sustainable performance is an emerging and more pertinent concept in human resource management. It highlights employee performance within the context of sustainability. De Jonge & Peeters (2019) contend that the evaluation of both job performance and employee health and well-being is crucial for promoting sustainable and forward-looking job performance. Peeters, Jonge, and Taris (2013) describe employee sustainable performance as the capacity to optimize both work-related accomplishments and the health and well-being of employees in the workplace.

The notion of Employee Sustainable Performance comprises two essential dimensions: employee performance and employee well-being. The two elements are interconnected, each exerting a long-term, reciprocal impact on overall employee performance. Ji et al. (2021) argue that this interaction highlights the necessity of implementing a dual approach that equally emphasizes both dimensions. Employee Sustainable Performance refers to an individual's ability to maintain elevated performance levels over prolonged durations while prioritizing their well-being.

Encouraging sustainable employee performance within firms produces multiple benefits. Organizations that prioritize sustainable employee performance are more likely to achieve heightened productivity, greater job satisfaction, and augmented profitability. Moreover, these organizations frequently exhibit diminished environmental consequences and enhanced social responsibility, hence advancing their overarching sustainability objectives (Dey, Bhattacharjee, Mahmood, Uddin & Biswas, 2022). Sustainable performance underscores the significance of dependability and consistency in an employee's contributions to work. It emphasizes employees' capacity to continually excel in various work situations and conditions over an extended period. This notion highlights both the quantifiable results of employee performance and their relationship with company goals. It generates a dedication to continuous

education and self-improvement, guaranteeing that personnel stay flexible and proficient in addressing future issues.

Ultimately, employee sustainable performance demonstrates a comprehensive strategy for employee management, focusing on the convergence of performance, health, and well-being to cultivate a more resilient and environmentally conscious workforce.

Employee Learning Orientation (ELO)

Learning orientation is defined as an organization's joint endeavor to create and apply knowledge, hence improving competitive advantages (Calantone, Roger, Cavusgil & Zhao, 2002). These initiatives involve the collection, distribution, and analysis of information to enhance the efficacy of individuals and organizations (Moorman & Miner, 1998; Mone, William & Vincent, 1998). Employee development is essential for adjusting to changing and competitive landscapes. In businesses, a learning orientation encourages people to seek challenges that provide chances for learning.

Research indicates that cultivating a supportive learning orientation for knowledge and skill acquisition favorably influences organizational outcomes (Brett & VandeWalle, 1999). A strong learning attitude enables employees to broaden their knowledge and assimilate it with other viewpoints from others (Harvey, Johnson, Roloff & Edmondson, 2019). Social cognition theory asserts that humans obtain knowledge and abilities through "enactive mastery experience" (personally doing a task or skill) and "mastery modeling" (observational learning from proficient models such as leaders) (Bandura, 1997). The attainment of knowledge and skills is affected by both intrinsic human variables and extrinsic situational circumstances. Leadership, an essential external aspect, profoundly influences the work environment and employee development (Oldham & Cummings, 1996). Transformational leadership, as articulated by Bandura (1997), is notably effective owing to its charismatic and inspirational qualities, motivating people to learn from and imitate these leaders.

Learning orientation consists of four dimensions: commitment to learning, shared vision, open-mindedness, and intra-organizational knowledge sharing (Calantone et al., 2002; Sinkula, Baker & Noordewier, 1997):

- *Commitment to Learning:* According to Sinkula et al. (1997) and Tajeddini (2009), commitment to learning is a reflection of an organization's dedication to facilitating the

acquisition of information through its employees and also to cultivating an environment that is conducive to learning. In accordance with this commitment, organizations consider learning to be an essential investment that is necessary for their continued existence and growth (Calantone et al., 2002).

- *Shared Vision*: According to Sinkula et al. (1997), a shared vision indicates that an organization has accumulated a unified focus on learning. According to Brown and Eisenhardt (1995), it is dependent on efficient internal communication, which enables departments to overcome communication hurdles, improve information flow, and synchronize operations across functions.
- *Open-Mindedness*: Open-mindedness refers to an organization's readiness to adopt novel concepts and persistently evaluate its current knowledge, assumptions, and practices (Sinkula et al., 1997; Nguyen & Barrett, 2006). This attribute is essential for embracing change and promoting creativity.
- *Intra-Organizational Knowledge Sharing*: Intra-organizational knowledge sharing entails the preservation and utilization of knowledge from diverse sources as a reference for future decision-making (Calantone et al., 2002). It necessitates an organization to undertake the reprocessing and reorganization of information systems. This dimension is essential for mitigating knowledge loss, especially during personnel turnover and transfers (Lukas, Bryan, Tomas, Hult & Ferrell, 1996).

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Based on the above theories and prior research, the following hypotheses were developed for our study:

H1: Transformational Leadership (TL) has a positive and significant effect on Employees' Sustainable Performance (ESP).

H2: Transformational Leadership (TL) has a positive and significant effect on Employees' Learning Orientation (ELO).

H3: Employees' Learning Orientation (ELO) has a positive and significant effect on Employees' Sustainable Performance (ESP).

H4: Employees' Learning Orientation (ELO) mediates the relationship between Transformational Leadership (TL) and Employees' Sustainable Performance (ESP) (The expected relationship is positive).

METHODOLOGY

Research Model

The quantitative research approach was utilized to investigate the correlation between transformational leadership and workers' sustainable performance, along with the mediating effect of employees' learning orientation in this correlation. The model illustrated in Figure 1 was created to ascertain the relationship between the variables.

Sample

The research population comprises personnel in the industrial zone of Elazığ province. The sample was obtained through convenience sampling, consisting of employees from a textile firm situated in the industrial area of Elazığ. The researcher utilized convenience sampling by selecting the most accessible and cost-effective individuals until the desired sample size was attained (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2005). Data for the research were gathered via in-person interviews utilizing structured survey instruments.

The final sample, including the exclusion of incomplete and erroneous data, comprised 280 male and 22 female participants, resulting in a total of 302 respondents. Table 1 displays the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

		Number	Percentage
Age	18-23 years	31	10,3
	24-30 years	27	8,9
	31-35 years	103	34,1
	36-50 years	139	46,0
	50 years and above	2	0,7

Marital Status	Married	265	87,7
	Single	37	12,3
Gender	Male	280	92,7
	Female	22	7,3
Education	Primary school	6	2,0
	High school	109	36,1
	Associate degree	117	38,7
	Bachelor's degree	53	17,5
	Other	17	5,6
Experience	1-3 years	42	13,9
	4-7 years	67	22,2
	8-11 years	118	39,1
	12 -16 years	66	21,9
	17 years and above	9	3,0

The distribution of participants' demographic characteristics is presented in Table 1. It was determined that 10.3% of the participants were between the ages of 18-23, 8.9% were between 24-30, 34.1% were between 31-35, and 46% were between 36-50. Additionally, 87.7% of the participants were married, while 12.3% were single. Regarding educational background, 92.7% of the participants were married, 2% had completed primary education, 36.2% had completed high school, 38.7% had an associate degree, and 17.5% held a bachelor's degree. In terms of professional experience, 13.9% of the participants had 1-3 years of experience, 22.2% had 4-5 years, 39.1% had 8-11 years, 21.9% had 12-16 years, and 3% had 17 years or more of experience.

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Data Collection Procedure

Transformational Leadership Scale: The Short Transformational Leadership Scale, developed by Berger, Romeo, Guardia, Yepes & Soria (2012) and validated in Turkish by Okan & Okan (2021), was used. This scale consists of a single dimension with 8 items. The reliability analysis indicated a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.748.

Employee Sustainable Performance Scale: The Employee Sustainable Performance Scale, developed by Ji et al. (2021) and adapted into Turkish by Çilhoroz, Topaktaş & Işık (2023), was employed. This scale consists of a single dimension with 10 items. The reliability analysis revealed a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.752.

Employee Learning Orientation Scale: The Employee Learning Orientation Scale, developed by Elliot & Church (1997) and utilized by Esin Yücel Karamustafa (2020), consists

of a single dimension with 5 items. The reliability analysis for this scale indicated a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.778.

In the study, all three concepts were measured using a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree).

Reliability Analysis

The study presents Cronbach's alpha values for the utilized variables in Table 1. Reliability analysis is used to assess the consistency of items within the scales. The Cronbach's alpha (α) coefficient, ranging from 0 to 1, is interpreted as follows (Tavşancıl, 2005):

- 0.00–0.40: The scale is not reliable.
- 0.40–0.60: Low reliability.
- 0.60–0.80: Quite reliable.
- 0.80–1.00: Highly reliable.

Accordingly, it is observed that the Transformational Leadership Scale, Employee Sustainable Performance Scale, and Employee Learning Orientation Scale used in the study have sufficient reliability levels.

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Table 2. Reliability of Measurement Tools

Variables	Alpha value
Transformational Leadership Scale	0,748
Employee Orientation Scale	0,778
Employee Sustainable Performance Scale	0,752

Analyses and Results

The data obtained in the study were analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for Windows 25.0 software. Descriptive statistical methods (frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation) were used to evaluate the data. In addition to normality tests, normality was assessed using histograms, Q-Q plots, and box-plot graphics, as well as distribution measures such as skewness, kurtosis, and coefficient of variation (Hayran & Hayran, 2011). For the data to be normally distributed, the values should align closely with the

45-degree line in the scatter plot, and the box should be centered around the median line in the box-plot (Büyüköztürk, 2011). Normality was checked using skewness and kurtosis values. Additionally, Mahalanobis distance was calculated, and multivariate normality was also checked. The results of both univariate and multivariate normality analyses indicated the presence of outliers. As a result, the outliers were removed from the dataset (n=69).

The scale scores were found to conform to the premise of normal distribution. Pearson correlation analysis was performed to investigate the relationship between continuous variables. Mediation analysis was conducted utilizing the Process Macro.

Reliability analysis is conducted to test whether the items in the scales show internal consistency with each other and whether all the items measure the same construct (Ural & Kılıç, 2006). In order for the test results to be reliable, the measurements themselves must be reliable. In this context, the reliabilities of the scales were examined using Cronbach's Alpha.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Kurtosis	Skewness	TL	ELO	ESP
TL	25,15	4,78	-0,374	-0,695	1,00		
ELO	16,65	3,74	-0,553	-0,757	r=0,695	1,00	
ESP	31,35	5,35	-0,424	-0,585	r=0,708	r=0,716	1,00

r= Pearson correlation analysis

Descriptive statistics for the measurement tools are presented in Table 3. Accordingly, the average for the Transformational Leadership Scale was calculated as 25.25±4.78, the Employee Orientation Scale as 16.65±3.74, and the Employee Sustainable Performance Scale as 31.35±5.35. Furthermore, a statistically significant positive relationship was found between the Transformational Leadership and the Employee Orientation ($r=0.695$; $p=0.000$). A statistically significant positive relationship was also found between the Transformational Leadership and the Employee Sustainable Performance ($r=0.708$; $p=0.000$). Additionally, a statistically significant positive relationship was found between the Employee Orientation and the Employee Sustainable Performance ($r=0.716$; $p=0.000$). When examining the skewness and kurtosis values for the measurement tools, it was determined that all values fell within the ± 1 range.

Table 4. Results Regarding the Mediation Role of EO in the Effect of TL on ESP

Model 1						
Independent	Dependent	β	S.H.	Std. β	t	p
Constatnt	ELO	2,972	0,831		3,574	0,000
TL		0,544	0,032	0,695	16,744	0,000
F-statistic=280,376; p-values=0,000; Adjusted R ² =0,481						
Model 2						
Independent	Dependent	β	S.H.	Std. β	t	p
Constatnt	ESP	11,428	1,167		9,791	0,000
TL		0,792	0,046	0,708	17,378	0,000
F-statistic=301,999; p-value=0,000; Adjusted R ² =0,500						
Constatnt	ESP	14,304	0,983		14,555	0,000
ELO		1,024	0,058	0,716	17,782	0,000
F-statistic=316,190; p-value=0,000; Adjusted R ² =0,512						
Model 3						
Independent	Dependent	β	S.H.	Std. β	t	p
Constatnt	ESP	9,586	1,071		8,950	0,000
TL		0,455	0,057	0,407	7,988	0,000
ELO		0,620	0,073	0,433	8,507	0,000
F-statistic=223,100; p-value=0,000; Adjusted R ² =0,596						
	Effect	SE	t	p	Lower bound	Upper bound
Total effect	0,792	0,046	17,378	0,000	0,703	0,882
Direct effect	0,455	0,057	7,988	0,000	0,343	0,567
Indirect effect	0,337	0,035			0,236	0,373

The initial model illustrates the impact of the transformational leadership on the employee orientation. The second model indicates the distinct impacts of the transformational leadership and the employee orientation on employee sustainable performance. The third model assesses the cumulative impact of the transformational leadership and the employee orientation on employee sustainable performance. The outcomes of the model assessed for mediation are detailed below:

- The Transformational Leadership has a statistically significant effect on Employee Orientation (mediator variable) (beta = 0.544, t = 16.744).
- The Employee Orientation has a statistically significant effect on Employee Sustainable Performance (dependent variable) (beta = 1.024, t = 0.716).

- When both the Transformational Leadership and the Employee Orientation are included in the regression analysis together, they affect the Employee Sustainable Performance (Transformational Leadership Scale beta: 0.455, $t = 7.988$ and Employee Orientation Scale beta: 0.482, $t = 8.507$).

The Transformational Leadership alone explains 50% of the variance in Employee Sustainable Performance, while the explanatory power of the model increased to 59.6% with the addition of the Employee Orientation. The third model, with the added variable, caused a 9.6% increase in explanatory power. While the mediator variable is included in the model, the relationship between the dependent and independent variables decreases. The total effect is 0.792, while the direct effect is 0.455 and the indirect effect is 0.337. Additionally, it was determined that the confidence interval does not include zero, indicating that the mediation is significant.

In the analysis conducted to understand whether the Employee Orientation mediates the relationship between the Transformational Leadership and the Employee Sustainable Performance, it was observed that when the Employee Orientation was included in the model (regression analysis), the relationship between the Transformational Leadership and the Employee Sustainable Performance remained significant. However, the beta coefficient of the Transformational Leadership decreased (as seen in the table, it decreased from 0.792 to 0.455 but remains significant). This indicates that the Employee Orientation partially mediates the relationship between the Transformational Leadership and the Employee Sustainable Performance. To test the significance of the mediation effect, a Sobel Test was applied. The test results showed that the mediation effect is significant ($z = 7.59$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis H4, which states that the Employee Orientation mediates the effect of the Transformational Leadership on the Employee Sustainable Performance is supported.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Leadership is an essential aspect of managerial duties. Organizational leaders can profoundly impact employee performance. Transformational leadership is a favored style in competitive markets because it effectively motivates people and fosters a corporate culture that prioritizes ethical practices as robust behavioral norms. Employees influenced by a transformational leadership style frequently endeavor to enhance the organization beyond specified job responsibilities and attain sustained performance levels over time.

The positive impact that transformational leadership has on the sustainable performance of employees is supported by our study, which makes a contribution to the research that has already been conducted. The most important contribution that it makes is the identification of the role that learning orientation plays as a mediator in the connection between transformative leadership and the sustainable performance of employees. It is the purpose of this article to examine the ways in which learning orientation and transformational leadership influence the sustainable performance of employees. Specifically, the purpose of this study is to investigate the function that employee learning orientation plays as a mediator in the relationship between transformational leadership and employee sustainable performance. According to the findings of our research, we have come to the conclusion that transformational leadership has a good impact on the sustainable performance of employees, and that employee learning orientation acts as a mediator of this effect.

In our research, each of the four hypotheses was found to be supported. The first result demonstrates that transformational leadership has a beneficial effect on the sustainable performance of employees of an organization. This finding is consistent with the findings of other studies that have investigated the connection between these two factors (Dvir, Eden, Avolio, and Shamir, 2002; Wang, Law, Hackett, Wang, and Chen, 2005; Al-Amin, 2017; Mangkunegara and Huddin, 2016; Ferozi and Chang, 2021). According to Dvir et al. (2002) and Wang et al. (2005), transformational leaders cultivate harmonious connections with their subordinates and make use of emotional tools (such as individual concern) to enhance the sense of belonging that employees have about their organization, which in turn leads to improved sustainable performance. (Al-Amin, 2017; Mangkunegara & Huddin, 2016) There is empirical research that supports the positive effect that transformational leadership has on employee job performance. This evidence highlights the importance of transformational leadership in the process of cultivating a workforce that is motivated, loyal, and high-performing. According to Ferozi and Chang (2021), transformational leaders are able to inspire their subordinates, foster creativity, innovation, and a sense of belonging, and contribute to an overall improvement in job performance through their actions and communication to their employees.

The second finding of the study demonstrates that transformational leadership has a positive effect on the learning orientation with which employees approach their work. These findings are in line with those of other research that have been conducted in the past. According to Slater and Narver (1995), the rationale behind this is that transformational leadership plays

a significant role in motivating employees to learn, to realize their full potential, and to push the boundaries of their learning. According to Sinkula et al. (1997), transformational leaders have a strong personal commitment to increasing their knowledge and skills. They inspire others around them to strive for learning and create behaviors that are learning-oriented.

The final two findings reveal that employee learning orientation positively impacts employee sustainable performance and mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and employee sustainable performance. These results are consistent with other studies in literature. Guided by social cognitive theory, transformational leadership prioritizes self-regulation and intrinsic motivation over external rewards, fostering personal development and a sense of purpose among employees (Wang et al., 2014). In this context, commitment to learning and skill development becomes critical. Defined as a dedication to developing one's abilities, learning orientation is effective in driving employee performance (Dweck, 2000). Consequently, when leaders adopt a transformational style and promote an open learning environment, employee performance can achieve sustainable success.

Managers and decision-makers can foster a feeling of belonging, enhance employee engagement, and promote sustainable success by implementing the concepts of transformational leadership. They can also enable employees to get enhanced engagement, sustainable performance, and efficient communication between staff and management. Management can enhance learning by cultivating and sustaining an organizational environment that fosters individual employees' learning initiatives, so reinforcing the connection between transformational leadership and sustainable employee performance. Organizations aiming to enhance employee performance sustainably should prioritize individuals eager to learn. They can develop training programs and coordinate mentoring seminars for their staff to enhance competencies. Ongoing education offers employees several opportunities to examine other viewpoints and acquire information for enduring performance.

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This study offers significant insights into the correlation among transformative leadership, employee learning orientation, and sustainable performance, although it possesses specific limitations. The study is confined to a single province (Elazığ) and one sector (textile), perhaps restricting the generalizability of the results. Future researchers are urged to investigate this study's subject across other companies, industries, and geographical areas. Furthermore, additional moderating variables must be investigated to solidify the connections between transformational leadership and its effects, including employee learning orientation and

sustainable performance. Longitudinal studies would be beneficial for examining the enduring impacts of transformational leadership and learning orientation on employee performance. Subsequent study should corroborate the suggested moderating model utilizing heterogeneous populations, research environments, and sectors with distinct attributes.

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